

PHONETIC COINCIDENCE AND SEMANTIC DIFFERENTIATION OF HOMONYMS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Toshtukhtayeva Maksuda

Termez State University, Faculty of foreign philology,
2nd year master's specialist in Linguistics (English language)
(Termez, Uzbekistan)

Annotation : This article identifies and examines phonetic similarities and semantic differences of homonyms in English language. One of the biggest difficulties in the English language, which everyone, without exception, faces, is that words with the same spelling or sound can have completely different meanings. Often, sentences with such words, that is, homonyms, confuse a person, since the translation of each word separately does not make it possible to understand the meaning of the sentence as a whole. This type of words is found in the language quite often, however, within the framework of the study of homonyms of the English language, the problem of homonymy remains poorly understood. The concept of homonymy is investigated and a comparative analysis of the phenomenon of homonymy in the English language is made. When choosing a word, you need to know its meaning, use, as well as compatibility with other words, in order to avoid misunderstandings.

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Introduction. The study of homonymy is especially important for understanding a foreign language, since in it different grammatical forms may have the same sound or spelling. In Modern English Studying of homonyms of words is one of the developing branches of lexicology nowadays. Homonyms reflect the general trend of simplification of a language. Homonymic meanings of words are closely connected with the development of modern informational technologies. Being a developing

branch of linguistics it requires a special attention of teachers to be adequated to their specialization in English. The investigation of homonyms and their differentiation with polysemantic words is not being still investigated in the sufficient degree and this problem is still waiting for its investigator. Our work is one another attempt to investigate this problem. A significant contribution to the study of the phenomenon of homonyms was made by some famous researchers A.I.Smirnitskiy, B.A. Ilyish, N. Buranov, V. V. Vinogradov, O. Jespersen, U.K. Yusupov, M. Dzhusupov, J. J. Jalolov and others [1].

In linguistics, homonyms are words that have the same spelling and pronunciation but different meaning. For instance: break- break, see- sea, braje- break, row- row and others. Homonyms be simultaneously homographs and homophones- that is to say they have identical spelling and pronunciation, but with different meanings. Examples are the words **carp** (to complain needlessly) and **carp** (the fish) have the same spelling:

- Rashad would tune out when his boss began to carp at him.
- Johanne's passion is fishing for trophy carp.

Bank (a financial establishment) and **bank** (the slope bordering a river)

- Go to the bank and deposit your paycheque.
- Jim and Janet went down to the river bank to admire the swans.

In English language homonyms may be homophones and homographs.

A homograph (from the Greek: ὁμός, homós, "same" and γράφω, gráphō, "write") is a word that shares the same written form as another word but has a different meaning. Homographs (literally "same writing") are usually defined as words that share the same spelling, regardless of how they are pronounced. If, when spoken, the meanings may be distinguished by different pronunciations, the words are also

heteronyms: Example of homographs are **sewer** (a conduit for waste) and **sewer** (a person who sews) sound quite different.

The sewer drains were backed up.

Novice sewers often buy their fabric on sale.

"Homophone" derives from Greek homo- (ὅμο-), "same", and phōnḗ (φωνή), "voice, utterance". A homophone is a word that is pronounced the same (to varying extent) as another word but differs in meaning. A homophone may also differ in spelling. The two words may be spelled the same, for example rose (flower) and rose (past tense of "rise"), or spelled differently, as in rain, reign, and rein. The term homophone may also apply to units longer or shorter than words, for example a phrase, letter, or groups of letters which are pronounced the same as another phrase, letter, or group of letters. Homophones that are spelled differently are also called heterographs, e.g. **to**, **too**, and **two**. Examples of homophones are **cent**, **scent** and **sent** differ in spelling:

When my grandmother emigrated to Canada, she didn't have a cent to her name.

Joe and Bridget's favourite movie is The Scent of Green Papaya.

The parcel was sent by courier [2].

Most words differ from each other in both spelling and pronunciation therefore they are called **allonyms**. Not so many linguists distinguish this category. But it must be admitted that Keith C. Ivey, in his discussion of homonyms, recognizes this fact and writes:

Those familiar with combinatorics may have noticed that there is a fourth possible category based on spelling and pronunciation: words that differ in spelling and pronunciation as well as meaning and origin (alligator/true). These pairs are technically known as **different words**.

Unfortunately, this seemingly neat solution doesn't work because all heteronyms are different words as Ivey's examples show. He illustrates homophones with

board/bored, clearly two different words though pronounced alike, and his example of homographs (the verb desert/the noun desert) again shows, by their pronunciation, that they are different words.

Even his example of a homonym - words having both the same sound and spelling, as illustrated by "to quail and a quail" - clearly shows they are different words. Lexicographers underline this point by writing separate entries for different words, whether or not they have the same spelling and pronunciation.

An allonym is a word that differs in spelling and pronunciation from all other words, whereas both homonyms and heteronyms identify words that are the same, in some ways, as other words. No doubt in ordinary usage, we will have little need for this term, although it would simplify lexical explanation if one could start by making the claim that the most words in English are allonyms. The clear exceptions are other groups. Different words that are spelled and pronounced the same which are correctly called homonyms proper but some writers, confusingly, call them heteronyms [3]. When different words are spelled the same way but pronounced differently, they belong to homographs and they are sometimes misleadingly called heteronyms. By contrast, when different words are pronounced the same way but spelled differently, we may properly call them homophones rarely, they have also been called heteronyms.

Homonyms proper are words, as I have already mentioned, identical in pronunciation and spelling, like fast and liver above. Other examples are: back n part of the body back adv away from the front back v go back; ball n a gathering of people for dancing ball n round object used in games; bark n the noise made by dog bark v to utter sharp explosive cries bark n the skin of a tree bark n

a sailing ship; base n bottom base v build or place upon base a mean; bay n part of the sea or lake filling wide-mouth opening of land bay

n recess in a house or room bay v bark bay n the European laurel [4].

Conclusion. In modern English language, the phenomenon of homonymy is widely developed. This phenomenon attracts many linguists to study its problems and

attempt to identify phonetic similarities and semantic differences of homonyms in the English language. But, despite the fact that the study of homonymy has been conducted for a long time, there is still neither generally accepted definition of homonyms, nor established terminology in this area. Taking into account the complexity of this approach, it turns out to be most expedient to refer to the dictionary and simply memorize the existing differences.

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